

Exiting with Fear: Public Sector Workers' Perception of Retirement Planning in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the perceptions of public sector workers on post-retirement plans in Nigeria and it was discovered that while there is no disagreement about the fact that retirement from formal employment is a major phase in an individual's life and a transition that requires careful planning and management, not much systematic thinking, and action especially at the level of the state in Nigeria have gone into the above. The study revealed that though a lot of studies have focused on retirement as a fact of life, not enough has been done in the later regard with respect to Nigeria and especially the situation regarding public service workers. The study utilized both the desk review of literature and the Key Persons Interviews (KPIs) in gathering information while focusing on public sector workers in three federal ministries. Purposive sampling technique through the snowball approach was also used in the study. Consequently, the study called for a retooling of the regulation and policy on retirement in the public sector in Nigeria to take cognisance of the fact that workers may not represent an undifferentiated and homogenous group. Policies need to take into cognisance the fact that retirement and what happens next will be affected by socioeconomic forces such as state of health at retirement, education, income bracket, social network and even religion.

Keywords: retirement, retirees, adjustment, mental health, policy, public service

Introduction

The study examines the perceptions of public sector workers on post-retirement plans in Nigeria. While there is no disagreement about the fact that retirement from formal employment is a major phase in an individual's life and a transition that requires careful planning and management, not much systematic thinking, and action especially at the level of the state in Nigeria have gone into the above. Even beyond the role of the state is the likely fact that retiring individuals are often literally caught by surprise at the fact that they would exit the service soon. This surprise results largely from the inadequate planning for this reality and even the fact that the propensity towards such planning may have been hindered by socio-structural factors often within and beyond the individual worker. There is no doubt that quite a lot of studies have focused on retirement as a fact of life (Borland, 2005; Henkens & van Solinge, 2021) and some scholars have also invested interest in looking at retirement and post-retirement life in general (Zacher & Rudolph, 2017; van Solinge, 2013; Munnell & Sass, 2009; Hornstein & Wagner, 1985; Damman & van Duijn, 2017). However, not enough has been done in the later regard with respect to Nigeria and especially the situation regarding public service workers. Therefore, the study here is an attempt to enrich our knowledge of the above situation and provide some empirical guidance on public policies and social work interventions focused on retirement in Nigeria. In addition, by focusing on a critical public issue the study hopes to contribute to the discourse of retirement and post-retirement plans especially from a developing nation perspective.

Unlike the issue of planning for retirement, quite a volume of attention has been paid to the health challenges and issues of the aged globally. As a matter of fact, the literature on gerontology whether from sociology, social work, psychology, public health or other allied disciplines have focused mainly on the various dimensions of the health of the aged (Abud, et al., 2022; Jowell, et al., 2020; Greer et al., 2022; Stenner et al., 2011; Amin, 2017; Maggi et al, 2021 etc.). The prominence of the above concern with aging is also captured in the fact that there has sprung up specialised journals that focus on aging and health (see for instance, Journal of Aging and Health; Aging and Health Research; Journal of Frailty and Aging etc.). As a result, the popular notion of successful aging is almost invariably related to health and health outcomes. However, the above concerns as important as they seem often generate an unconscious focus on health as the primary (and even only) challenge of the aged in the society. As a result, the issue of the transition from end of career to another lifestyle and the impact of this on the health and psychological wellbeing of the aged and soon to be aged is not given adequate attention.

The above situation, which does not disown some efforts towards capturing the end of career challenges of the aging, is probably more evident in the developing parts of the world where economic and social problems of living make such a concern apparently unimportant. Perhaps the discipline of social work in Africa is more guilty of the above omission than any other academic or professional discipline in the continent. Therefore, a focus on the career ending worries and problems of the aged in the continent is imperative. Such imperative seems reinforced by the fact that structural and economic

challenges of nations in the continent may have generated a scenario where such concerns regarding what happens to the older people when they retire from their careers may seem a superfluous concern in the face of other immediate and pressing needs ranging from youth unemployment, food insecurity to poor or unstable economies and internal insecurity.

The examination of post-retirement plans of workers seem further justified by the fact that attitudes and decisions regarding retirement as a phase in life are affected by contextual and social factors (see, Moen, 1996; Behr & Bennet, 2007). Therefore, the decision over what to do at retirement and attitudes/feelings regarding impending end of career retirement are expected to be affected by forces operating at the domestic/household, social/political and organizational/economic contexts. Thus, the plans one make, lack of planning as well as anxieties about retirement may be produced by forces beyond and outside the control of the individual worker.

Perhaps, asking people about their retirement plans rather than seeming like bothering them with an obvious fact (i.e. that people would make such plans) would seem in line with the realization that often delusion, confusion and fantasy may muddle an individual's perception of their roles/selves in the future (Quoidbach et al., 2013). Therefore, such an exercise in addition to enabling workers exorcise the 'demons' of an unknown future and encourage them to come to terms with retirement not as a form of end of work activity but rather a transition that is necessary.

In addition, there can be no gainsaying the need for research to consistently focus on retirement issues given their dynamism and rapid fluidity overtime. As has been argued, "since the middle of the 20th century, there have been too many changes in retirement and pension arrangements for researchers to become complacent about a fixed future" (Henkens et al., 2018:805).

Despite the above, there is probably a dearth of studies on work after retirement in the extant literature (Beehr & Bennet, 2014). This is despite the fact that gerontologists are largely agreed on the value of such research (Cooper & Beehr, 2015). Incidentally, the above concerns have eluded the attention of social workers and gerontologists in Nigeria. The situation is even more vacuous in the case of retirement planning by workers. Therefore, the current study hopes not only to add to the body of knowledge on retirement from a developing country perspective but equally respond to the obvious lacuna in knowledge.

Retirement, Retirement Planning and Work-Retirement Transition

There exists quite a robust literature on retirement. This is unsurprising since issues of retirement and post-retirement plans and lifestyles have attracted attention not only from scholars (of gerontology, demography, social work, sociology, economics, psychology etc.) but even from policy makers, public administrators, and the generality of the practice community. The diversity of perspectives from which these issues have been pursued underlines the importance retirement and issues involving it assume in modern society. The views expressed in the extant literature can be loosely organised around such themes as the meaning/conceptualization of retirement, the role of technology in retirement; role of human resources (availability and otherwise), retirement policies and plans, sociocultural and structural influences on retirement and post-retirement life, post-retirement life in general etc.

Interestingly, Denton & Spencer (2008) have found out that conceptions of what retirement is or entails varies along a continuum that "reflect nonparticipation or reduced participation in the labour force, receipt of pension income, end-of-career employment, self-assessed retirement, or combinations of those characteristics" (Denton & Spencer, 2008:1). As a result, retirement lends itself to a good number of meanings to different people in different contexts. But despite these various meanings, it generally describes the end of something (work; career) and perhaps the readiness to begin another phase of life. Even among those who self-describe or self-assess themselves as retired there is that undoubted conception of the end of an important phase of work life. There is no doubt that retirement may be viewed as a complex process which has been unfolding over time but vary considerably across individuals (Szinovacz, 2012). Therefore, retirement is not simply a job – related or economic phenomena which naturally happens. It is rather a much more defining and multi-dimensional process that embodies not only an economic dimension but social implications. This calls then for a careful management cum planning of the work-retirement transition.

Given its complex nature, some concepts have been used by scholars to describe this process (retirement). Among these include 'phased retirement' i.e., this allows workers who are approaching the statutory age of retirement to reduce hour put in work but remain with the same employer (see, Hutchens, 2010; Cahill et al., 2015). Also used but in capturing the transition from career employment and eventual withdrawal from the labour force is the concept of 'bridge retirement'. As the name suggests, it is paid employment that older workers take up at the end of their career jobs before deciding to withdraw totally from the labour force (Zang, et al., 2009; Cahill, et al., 2006). The above which has equally been labelled 'unretirement' or 'reversing retirement' (Ruhm, 1990; Maestas, 2010) may be used in capturing retirement plans that involve getting engaged in new forms of employment and or working for new employer at the official cessation of career employment elsewhere.

Incidentally, studies show that participation in work as well as engagement in social and community life improves the mental and physical health of the aged and help them increase self-esteem and sense of belonging (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2011; Savage & Bailey, 2004). Thus, a good number of studies focus on the psychological factors and processes that precede retirement (see, Feldman & Behr, 2011; Adams & Raul, 2011; Wang & Shultz, 2010). These studies as important as they seem, often just concentrate on the factors limited to the worker concerned viz. financial comfort, health and personal expectations influencing or mediating retirement. Thus, they often do not account for the larger social and economic/organizational factors that may play significant roles in the retirement process. Hence, apart from the awareness that retirement is not simply an individual affair (Pienta, 2003), there is need to understand that decisions including plans

about retirement take place within the social context of the individual especially the household/family situation of the worker (Ho & Raymo, 2009; Denaeghel et al, 2011).

Interestingly, studies show that on the average, healthy, educated workers especially males who also do not have private pension (private savings towards retirement) who leave service at relative younger ages are likely to seek new challenges either as wage earners or self-employed (Behr & Bennet, 2015; Alcover, 2017). In other words, such people are moved to seek new sources of economic returns in addition to taking a break from career employment. It is expected that the above scenario may capture the Nigerian situation where public or civil servants are kept on earnings that, given steep inflation and national economic downturns make savings almost impossible.

The transitory nature of retirement entails in effect that it is not simply the end of a particular phase of life but more importantly the beginning of another phase of life or what has been labelled 'third age' by Gilleard & Higgs (2005). However, the success of such transition or commencement of the symbolic third age depends on the preparation or plans made towards such a future by the worker. Also, evidence in the literature suggests that adjustment to retirement and the quality of life thereafter are commonly measured through emotions and perceived wellbeing of the retirees (van Solinge, 2013; Wang & Shil, 2014; Hornstein & Wagner, 1985; Barbosa et al., 2016). Thus, the expression of anxiety, fears or even uncertainty over retirement points to a likely psychological or emotional imbalance on the part of the individual. While such concerns would ordinarily be consigned to the attention of psychologists there is no debate that social gerontologists especially those with social work background can find useful niche through designing effective post-retirement intervention programmes for retirees. Such interventions while benefitting from the rapidly growing body of knowledge about retirement would crucially factor in the social and structural influences on retirement and adjustment to retirement in developing societies.

There is no gainsaying that we live now in a world of rapid technological changes. Technological devices have so penetrated our lives that often we are seemingly oblivious of their existence even while in their full grips. Along the above lines, there has been attempts towards understanding the influences of technology on the process of aging (Thompson & Mayhorn, 2012). The discussion of retirement goes along with the issue of aging since both are not mutually exclusive and retirement apart from being age-pegged entails the entry into what is considered advanced age in most societies. Retirement age is usually set at that age that society perceives that the capacity of the individual to work has likely been impaired by age whether physically or mentally or both.

However, despite the number of studies that have examined how different work environments produced by technology especially blended work environments impact on older workers (Thompson & Mayhorn, 2012; Zhan, 2016), no direct effect of technology on retirement adjustment has been recorded. Despite the above obvious lacuna, Wang & Shil (2014) offer good insights on how technology can impact on retirement adjustment outcomes especially the psychosocial wellbeing of retirees. Therefore, the impact of technology on retirement and retirement plans should elicit more research focus. At a minimum, technology may exert both negative and positive influences on retirement. In this sense, the avalanche of new technological devices may spur the enthusiasm of the retiree to get involved in one form of technology driven activity or the other. At the same time, such array of technological devices may draw the helplessness and resignation of the retiree who may feel intimidated and incapable of being part of a technology driven new world. However, the role of technology, one way or the other can be seen as severely limited in the case of Nigeria given the relative low level of technological penetration in the country.

While there may be attraction for retired workers who see themselves as fit to seek some form of further employment even if in another sector, such a decision may be constrained by the job market realities confronting such people. Specifically, studies generally point towards the fact that employers are usually not eager to either hire or retain older workers (Munnell & Sass, 2009; van Dalen et al, 2015; Conen et al., 2012). The above situation is true in the developing world as it is in Western societies. Apart from the economics of relationship between labour cost and productivity or the marginal productivity of such workers, there is a general stereotyping of older workers that range from being slow, unproductive, with low physical and mental capacities to often coping with health challenges and low initiative.

However, a failure to plan may predictably result in adjustment problems and psychological imbalance. As has been shown by Hershey & Henkens (2014) a lack of control [by workers] over retirement transition may be consistent with reduced wellbeing and problems of retirement adjustment. In other words, while one may canvass for structural and institutional approaches to retirement adjustment especially in developing societies, the individual worker approaching retirement should seek to control the transition. Such control may be enhanced by timely and proper planning as retirement approaches.

Studies also show that earning insufficient income (scenario that confronts pensioners in Nigeria) and the mere fact of being without job exert negative influence on life satisfaction (Zenger et al., 2010; Li et al., 2013). The above is especially the case when the retiree feels that she still has many productive years in her system. As have been argued by Kim & Hall (2013) retirement does not necessarily entail end of work. A fact clearly buttressed by the reality that elderly people tend to continue to work or engage in post-retirement jobs (Zhan et al., 2015).

While there is extensive literature on aging and retirement, there is ambivalence in the literature about what retirement really means (Henkens & van Solinge, 2021; Chambre & Netting, 2018). Such indicators ranging from statutory age of retirement, reduction in work hours, receiving of pension to total withdrawal from the labour force and change of employer have all been used in conceptualising retirement. However, in cognisance of the literature and statutory provisions in Nigeria, we define retirement in this study as those who have attained the mandatory age of 60 years or given 35 years of service as clearly stated by extant public sector policy on retirement in the country. But it is interesting to note that a good number of

people attain the above benchmarks (especially 35 years of service) while still mentally and physically strong and able to contribute to the labour force. It is in view of the above that retirement planning aimed at a seamless transition from end of career retirement to some other economic and/or social roles become important.

Theoretical Framing

A lot of theories have emerged overtime in the attempts of scholars to understand and explain retirement and its dynamics. In other words, there is a plethora of theoretical viewpoints in the extant literature that focus on retirement from active service or work. Some of these theories are anchored on biological and health factors and generally focus on the degeneration and or weakening of the human body as the individual ages. However, despite their merits in explaining aging and retirement, we would focus on the social science explanation which anchor the issue on the social system or social environment of the individual and factors therein. This is expected, given that the paper is based on the social forces that impinge or influence retirement plans in a developing society like Nigeria. Even from the social sciences perspective a couple of theories have been proffered in explaining the reality and necessity of retirement as well as what comes after it or the adjustment issues associated with it. Despite the above, we would only highlight a few of these theories before arriving at the one that nest captures the goals of this paper. Perhaps, the most prominent and commonly used theories in the above regard are the activity theory, the continuity theory, and the disengagement theory.

The Activity theory - this theory is generally seen is emanating from the efforts of sociologists of the symbolic interactionist's perspective at the University of Chicago. It examines aging from the position of role flexibility and contends that as one ages some roles are discontinued, others are intensified and some are intensified with efforts (Havighurst, 1968; Chakrabarti, 2009; Barrow & Smith, 1979). But important for us here is that the theory argues that productive aging only occurs when older people remain active and maintain or continue social interactions. This aligns with the view that a measure of well-adjusted aging is through being active (Pande, 2009). The above contention is equally captured in the view that the individual's activity viz-a-viz. the social sphere is the substance of life for people at all ages (Barrow & Smith, 1979). Thus, total withdrawal from such social substance of life as may be occasioned by retirement can be certainly harmful to the individual.

Disengagement theory – this relatively old viewpoint is premised on the unalienable assumption that growing old is only natural. Thus, given that people will naturally grow older if they live long, society should adopt a system that disengages old people from activities in the society including work. In effect, it suggests that people, as they age, lose their activeness and play largely inactive roles as a result of age (Decker, 1980). So, the theory canvasses that it is better for such people to withdraw from activities and for society to keep such people away from these activities. Thus, almost in all cultures and society there is the inevitable withdrawing or severe decrease in involvement of old people in societal activities including work for a couple of reasons (Stein & Moritz, 1999; Cummings & Henry, 1961). Disengagement is often premised on the need to create space for the younger generation and even make society better. In other words, retirement of the aged naturally creates opportunity for the younger people who with their energy, current knowledge and technological skills bring overall innovation, creativity and increase the productivity of society (Thompson, et al, 2012).

However, while the theory of disengagement may be supported by the decreasing energy, physical and mental limitations often generated by aging, it may unwittingly support a docile and supine aged population and even a perception of the aged as parasites which may be counterproductive. Equally, the disengagement theory has been criticised also for emphasizing social withdrawal which is inconsistent with the fact that a primary element of life satisfaction is being in meaningful relationship and activities (Neumann, 2000; Baltes, 1987). It is equally accused of glossing over the sociocultural and environmental factors that may affect the decision to withdraw (see, Marshall, 1996). According to DeLiema & Bengtson (2015), activity and disengagement theories were the first theories that sought to utilise social science data in the explanation of why some people are more adaptive or successful in meeting the multiple and inevitable challenges that come with aging more than others.

Continuity Theory – This theory is anchored on the views that retirement does not mean end of work involvement; elderly people usually engage in post-retirement jobs often closest to their previous careers; and even make new friends that are like their previous mates; and use retirement to engage in activities prioritised as important to them (Cooper & Beehr, 2015; Zhan et al., 2015; Gobeski & Beehr, 2009; Pushkar et al., 2010). As succinctly captured by Atchley (1989) continuity theory places premium on the employment of familiar strategies by retirees to maintain continuity. Continuity is defined broadly as going beyond strictly economic or pecuniary engagements but including other activities which sustain both the sociability of the individual and enhance her social functioning.

So, retirement signals some continuity even if that may not be in activities defined from the economic perspective. An albatross of this theoretical viewpoint is that while viewing discontinuity as mainly a problem, it sees continuity from the opposite light as positive (see, Lynch et al., 2016). Despite the above, the theory has been commonly utilised by scholars in studies of both post-retirement life and successful aging (Lu & Shelley, 2019; Ejechi, 2015; Zacher & Rudolph, 2017; Bedaso & Han, 2021).

However, despite the strengths of these three theories, this study finds the 'transition to retirement' model (Borland, 2005) very pertinent. In this scheme, Borland provides what can be termed a good schematic model for thinking through retirement. For him, there is need to distinguish between two main periods viz. that in which "career employment" is the individual's main activity and a later stage of "retirement". But lying between these two is what he labels the "transition phase". This transition phase can start at various ages [though related to prescribed age at retirement or the individual's wish] and vary in length. This phase is usually characterised by reduction in labour force attachment on the part of the person

concerned (this may take the form of fewer hours of work, change in work location including working from home, assuming tasks that are less demanding, and ultimately the receipt of pension benefits). In the case of public sector workers in Nigeria who are very much aware of the termination of employment at the age of 60, it is expected that a reasonable phase of transition (including thinking and planning) should occur from the age of fifty (thinking about it and some planning) and fifty-five (acute awareness and planning towards retirement). Thus, workers who have five years or less to retire from service are supposedly caught up in this planning for retirement or transition phase.

Materials and Methods

The study utilized both the desk review of literature and the Key Persons Interviews (KPIs) in gathering information. The study focused on public sector workers in three federal ministries viz. Ministry of Finance; Ministry of Works; and the Ministry of Women Affairs. A total of 45 respondents (i.e., 15 from each ministry) were selected from workers in these ministries in the Federal Secretariat Lagos. The collection of data was through the Key Persons Interviews. Thus, the study utilised the purposive sampling technique through the snowball approach focusing on three critical factors viz. workers who would retire between the time of the study and the next three years; accessibility for the study; and gender equity.

The choice of those approaching retirement was guided by the goal of the study to unravel the perceptions of such workers including situational factors and anxiety/ apprehensions that confront these workers who literally have a foot at the door already. These respondents were interviewed between October and December 2023 and the interviews took place in designated venues chosen by the respondents including their offices, homes, and canteens. In all, the study interviewed twenty-seven male and eighteen female workers which is more than a fair distribution considering the ratio of male to female workers in the public sector in Nigeria. All the interviewees were aged from fifty-five (included in the sample were those to retire on attaining the mandatory 35 years of employment and may not have attained the chronological age of 60) to fifty-nine years. The study obtained the informed and voluntary consent of the respondents who were assured of confidentiality and strict utilization of the information for research purposes only. Furthermore, as the study was carried out with human beings, ethical clearance was gotten from the Directorate of Strategic Contacts, Ethics and Publications office of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka with clearance code: UNN/EC/015/1DS-01/APR-24

Findings of the Study

Planning for Imminent Retirement

This section presents the findings from the study i.e., the perceptions of respondents regarding their impending retirement from career work. The opinions expressed generally revealed that a couple of factors ranging from personal/familial situations, economic/financial considerations to expectations of free time upon retirement influence the decision to plan or not to plan and even the nature of such plans. However, very dominant in the above, going from the position adopted by a majority of the respondents is that the tendency to plan is mainly related to perceived financial adequacy. In other words, workers see retirement planning in Nigeria as largely a function of financial resources. The perceptions of the respondents are presented below.

The 'Economics' behind Retirement Planning:

In this sub-section, the study reveals the perception of respondents who anchored their retirement planning or lack of planning on economic considerations especially in the sense of not having the economic or financial resources to plan anything. Typically, representing the above is the sentiment, *"my dear, I have honestly not thought about it [retirement plan] even though I am not unaware that it is a matter of three years now. But where is the resources for any reasonable planning. I don't want to deceive myself and stress over what looks hopeless now given [that there is] no money"*. Also, agreeing with the above opinion, another respondent stated, *"who wants to plan anything on a salary that is very meagre. I know I will retire soon but given my economic situation, I will let things sort themselves out. Things could change for the better tomorrow, and I would have the financial muscle for such planning"*. Equally, another respondent, a female senior administrative executive offers, *"I have made some arrangements; I have even procured some materials for my next business after here. However, I am not sure that I would have enough money to effectively take off, though I plan to source for credit from one or two of these online lenders"*.

The above sentiments actually confirm the report in the popular Financial Times about how economic crunch and hardship are making Nigerians fall prey to the activities of all manner online financial agencies with their antics. The influential London newspaper captioned its report in November of 2023, *"Nigerians resort to emergency loans as austerity and inflation bite"* and almost concludes that this seem to be the new normal for many struggling and marginal citizens in the country. Incidentally, for a senior civil servant who has put in decades of service in the country's service to hinge her post-retirement plans on this source says a lot about the general privation in the country.

However, one of the respondents who claimed to be an assistant director in his ministry put the financial constraint in proper perspective when he stated, *"if a top civil servant like me cannot effectively discuss my retirement plans less than two years to it, it means that the financial resources for such do not exist. I have not saved anything significant that can warrant such plans and I do not want to plan in the air. It worries me for sure, but I hope that friends would step in and help somehow when the time comes"*.

Dependence on Primordial Links:

Interestingly, several respondents hinged their retirement plans on what may be called primordial planks especially friends and families. Thus, a lady clerical officer was forthright in stating, *“my main hope of survival and doing anything when I leave service is on my children. I mean what I receive here every month is usually not even enough for our needs. But I thank God that my children are now doing well on their own, so the burden would soon be their own to bear”*.

This is not out of place especially in view of the sociocultural values and expectations in which children are often regarded as investments for the family. So, in this frame of reasoning parents train their children so that these children would in turn take care of them in old age. The above sentiments were reinforced by a significant number of the respondents who stated that their plans hinge around depending on children and family members for what comes next. According to one of these respondents, *“my children are already working towards setting up a small supermarket for me once I retire. They said they will not allow me stay at home idle especially since we lost their mother five years ago”*.

Fears and Anxiety about Retirement:

While retiring from work may ordinarily signal a happy event since not all who started working with the individual are either well or alive to welcome such an event, there is often the palpable fear in the individual regarding what comes next after retirement. In this case, despite all the intention to prepare adequately for retirement on the part of the individual and the fact that retirement age or time is a factor that the worker is often aware of even at the onset of employment, this transition may still occasion anxiety and foreboding bordering essentially on not being prepared and not certain about what life holds for the individual after the active working life. The above scenario was captured in the responses of a good number of the respondents. Hence, *“I must be sincere with you, I am very much afraid of what I would do after retirement. In fact, I consciously avoid thinking about it since it usually makes me gloomy”*.

Along the same lines, another respondent, a senior technical officer stated, *“I fear for my future after retirement. Unfortunately, I lost my only son some years ago and I do not have much of a family to rely on. I am the only light in my extended family. I just believe God would make a way”*.. Equally, *“of course, I am both uncertain and afraid about what would happen when I leave service in about three years. I just hope and pray that something good comes out of all the promises from the government to labour, so that I can at least save some money for retirement”*.

However, bringing in a spiritual dimension, another respondent opines, *“as a human being I fear about that post-retirement tomorrow, but I leave it all I the hands of God. No situation is beyond God and my problem is only a small matter to him”*. Incidentally, the above sentiments and even those of a good number of the respondents show how even the most mundane things are elevated into the concerns of God. It comes from a deep religiosity among the people of the country. Even cursory observers would readily attest to the deep influence of religion in the country. Nigerians are probably one of the most religious people on earth. As a result, some of the respondents really hope on God to somehow interfere and plan their retirement for them.

Retirement Planning and Mental Health:

Evident from the findings is that there is no one to one or direct relationship between inadequate retirement planning and mental health. However, the expressions of fear and anxiety were rife in the opinions of the respondents. As a matter of fact, such sentiments expressed by respondents in the preceding subsection like, *“I fear for my future”*, *“I fear about post-retirement”*, *“I am very much afraid”* pointed towards a psychological imbalance that could be related to the mental health of the individuals concerned. Therefore, while it is difficult to posit a direct relationship between concerns about post-retirement life and mental health, there is no doubt that the common or general feelings of anxiety and fear about what comes after retirement do not bode well for the mental health and psychological balance of these workers. Even those of the respondents who did not use words like fear and anxiety expressed feelings of uncertainty and degrees of unclarity about what would happen to them after cessation of formal employment in the public sector.

Leisure and Free Time Focus:

Some of the soon to be retired workers (about five in all) were more interested in the leisure and free time offered by retirement than any elaborate plans about what comes next. In the views of one of such people, *“honestly, I have no plans and do not want to worry myself yet. I want to take one or two months and sleep like nobody’s business. No more waking early and rushing off to work”*.

Some others were bogged down by health issues that they did not see planning for retirement in terms of other activities to take up as relevant in their situation. Typically, one of such people stated matter-of-factly, *“my dear, my health comes before any other thing. I have been struggling with severe health challenges in the last four years. So, when I retire, it would be time to rest and focus on my health. I have had enough of work and the troubles that come with it”*. The above views of a self-admitted chronically ill worker perhaps reflect the popular idioms that planning is only for those alive and that health comes first. Therefore, planning for retirement is largely a function of being mentally and physically fit at retirement.

Other Issues in Retirement Planning:

Preparation for retirement, it would appear has been affected by the social and structural realities confronting these workers. Incidentally, these realities have been largely economic in nature and hinge on the inability of the workers to save money with which to pursue post-retirement life. Despite the above which appear very general among those interviewed, some of the workers stated that they are already making plans towards retirement. According to one of these workers, *“I started planning for retirement three years ago. I would leave service by August next year and I have made moves with two of my friends to start a business outfit here in Lagos. I just hope it works”*. However, most of the plans and goals of these soon to retire workers are to look for paid employment even if at lower levels and lower pay in the private sector. According to one of those in this group, *“I have started brushing up my CV and making contacts among friends in the private sector. This is Lagos, something will happen, and I don't mind how small or lower it is compared to where I am now. I just need to be doing something”*.

Another respondent ambivalently stated, *“sure, I think about such a plan every time. It is a matter of nine months for me to leave and as you can see, I am hale and hearty, so I cannot just retire and fade away, something must happen”*. But when pressed further on exactly what he plans to do after retirement, the respondent could not provide any clear answer. All he could offer was that there are a number of options open to him but the kind of support he receives from family and friends would determine whatever it would be. This is a statement that clearly conveys uncertainty and the apprehension of the respondent about retirement and what comes after it.

Interestingly, only roughly ten percent of our respondents related their post-retirement plans to the compulsory pension fund workers contribute. Incidentally, such references were tinged with doubts over the availability of such funds and the ability of the retirees to access these funds. In the words of one these people, *“we make contributions for pension and if the money is there at retirement, it could be a deciding factor about what one can do next. I will not just sit at home moping as the days go by”*. Another while not doubting the existence of the money in the fund was rather sceptical about accessing such fund, thus, *“from what I have heard it is difficult and challenging to get the pension money from these PFAs, they are fond of mounting unnecessary obstacles and often the retired person may die without clearing all these hurdles and accessing the money”*.

It is instructive that despite the existence of a much-publicised pension scheme in Nigeria, a lot of the respondents primarily anchor their retirement plans on their own direct efforts or sources; followed by primordial networks like children, friends and families. Even religion [God] plays a major role in such plans and hopes for tomorrow way ahead of the contributory pension scheme. Perhaps, the above apart from reaffirming the huge influence of sociocultural norms (which prioritises primordial linkages in tackling the problem of the individual) and the noted religiosity of Nigerians equally call attention to the problems or challenges associated with the pension scheme. Some of the respondents referred to these challenges especially the bottlenecks associated with accessing the contributions as well as corruption (the general bane of public institutions in the country). However, the above challenges are not insurmountable, and a good number of retirees have accessed their contributions, but the issue may be a product of the still alien nature of institutional contributory schemes to workers in the country.

Discussion of Findings

The findings indicate that despite facing the same issue of apparent retirement from career jobs, these individuals reflect varying approaches to it. This resonates with the earlier contention that though retirement is a complex phenomenon, it varies considerably across individuals (Szinovacz, 2012). Equally significant is that our findings, given the number of times respondents invoked support from their children in planning retirement, contradict the findings of Damman & Diujn (2017) that only a minority of retirees experienced support from their children. This difference may be squarely down to sociocultural differences between the focus of our study (Nigeria, Africa) and that of the above authors. However, the above call attention to more cross-cultural studies of the phenomenon of retirement.

However, the finding regarding the dependence of respondents on primordial links especially family for their retirement plans is in tandem with the extant literature that point at the role of the household and family on the retirement process and decision (see, Damman, et al., 2011; Ho & Raymo, 2009). Additionally, the findings also show that a good number of workers anchor their retirement plans on taking up other jobs especially in the private sector. The above seem to confirm the sentiments in the literature that older workers at the end of their careers may take up other jobs (bridge retirement) before withdrawing totally from the labour force (Zang et al., 2009; Cahill, et al., 2006). The above phenomenon of ‘bridge retirement’ and even ‘reversing retirement’ (Maestas, 2010; Ruhm, 1990) may be perceived as dominating the retirement plans of public sector workers in Nigeria.

Equally emanating from the findings of the study is the openly expressed and palpable climate of anxiety and fears about what comes next (after retirement) among these respondents. This seems to validate the fact that the mental and physical health of the aged or retirees are tied to concerns about tomorrow or post-retirement life. In other words, inadequate retirement planning exerts negative effects on both mental and physical health of workers. The above is consistent with earlier findings and positions in the extant literature (see, Bedaso and Han, 2021; Abud et al, 2022; Savage and Bailey, 2004; Wang and Shi, 2014).

It is evident from the presentation that some of the perceptions of the respondents which tilt towards work engagement after retirement may seem in tune with the continuity theory. However, one still opts for the ‘transition to retirement’ model (Borland, 2005) since it captures the transition phase between career employment and retirement. This phase enables the

workers prepare for eventual withdrawal from service. And as our findings indicate, an overwhelming majority of the respondents by admitting to making plans or thinking about what to do at retirement despite the influencing factors are caught in a transition phase. Moreover, the respondents are still working (though approaching retirement) and cannot realistically be used to bear out the tenets of continuity theory since there is usually a difference between intention (prior to retirement) and action (after retirement).

Conclusion

Incidentally, the retirement age of 60 in the public service in Nigeria entails that a lot of people will retire still with enough energy and even capacity to live an active life. Despite a relatively low life expectancy in the country, the age of sixty remains relatively young for one to be consigned into a life of idleness for the rest of his or her life. Interestingly, those within the same age in the West are still viewed as active members of the society and as those with the experience and capacity to enrich policy making and service delivery in different spheres of life. But post-retirement planning in terms of the new roles or economic engagement the retiree chooses goes beyond the mere availability of resources – money for instance. In this case, planning and psychological readiness generate effective utilization of such resources and more crucially ensure the involvement of such retirees in activities that promote their health and psychological wellbeing i.e., activities that do not task their mental and physical capacities.

However, it is important to point out that retirement even at a relatively young age of 60 should not necessarily involve taking another employment or involvement in another economic or income earning activity. Post-retirement may undoubtedly involve a continuous identification with work or such a desire, a focus on active leisure, community service, further self-development (pursuit of otherwise repressed self-actualization goals) and even pronounced religious devotion (especially in Nigeria where religion is an oversubscribed phenomenon among the people).

Therefore, policies need to fathom the fact that retirement and what happens next will be affected by socioeconomic forces such as state of health at retirement, education, income bracket, social network and even religion. They need to be nuanced to capture these fine distinctions among workers. For instance, the emerging practice of allowing workers to choose their retirement age in some societies in the West may be worth examining in the above regard.

Thus, while there has been noted ambivalence about the viability of differentiated retirement approach (see for instance, Vandenberghe, 2023), it is emerging strongly as a tool for dealing with socioeconomic and structural challenges of strict age retirement. Interestingly, France and Germany are already leading in this approach with retirement ages varying between 62 – 67 years and 60 – 67 years respectively. Similarly, raising the retirement age has also been proposed for a country like China that has experienced increased average life span (see, Tieding and Hang, 2016). The idea is to set a minimum threshold for retirement and allow the individual to extend this depending on health and social factors confronting her. This method could inform policies in Nigeria in the sense of allowing workers to choose early or late retirement. This would surely work with the present direct contribution (DC) pension scheme in the public service since working longer would also entail contributing more to the pension fund and limiting the annual payout from the scheme. This policy option should be seriously considered as Nigeria grapples with multifaceted social and economic challenges.

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